

EFFECT OF MELT COMPOUNDING CONDITIONS AND CLAY ORGANIC MODIFIERS ON MORPHOLOGY OF COPOLYAMIDE NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

Hybrids with different types of organoclay were produced by melt compounding using different extrusion rates, in order to point out the effects of both processing conditions and hybrid composition on morphology of nanocomposites. All melt-intercalated samples were submitted to rheological, structural (TEM) and thermal measurements.

Keywords: copolyamide nanocomposites, melt compounding, extrusion rates, rheological analysis, morphology.

INTRODUCTION

The reinforcement of polyamides with nanometric layered silicates represents nowadays an innovative strategy to produce high performance plastics with enhanced structural and functional properties [1]. It is well known that the final properties are strictly correlate with the nanoscale arrangement of the silicate layers inside the polymer matrix as well as the entity of polymer-clay interactions. In this frame, great industrial and scientific attention is paid to polyamide-based nanocomposites prepared by melt compounding. Nevertheless, the difficulty in conveniently tuning materials and processing parameters to control the developed nanomorphology represents a great limit for the application of polyamide based nanocomposites on industrial scale [2]. In this work polymer- silicate nanocomposites were prepared by melt compounding using a commercial polyamide 6-based copolymer, with a partially aromatic structure, as thermoplastic matrix.

This study focuses on the possibility to improve performances of polyamide nanocomposites through conveniently tuning materials and processing conditions in melt compounding. Hybrids were submitted to rheological, structural and thermal analysis in order to point out the effects of both extrusion rates and polymer-clay affinity on morphology of nanocomposites.

EXPERIMENTAL

Two different organoclay were used as filler: Cloisite 30B (a layered sodium montmorillonite organically modified by methyl, tallow, bis-2- hydroxyethyl, and quaternary ammonium chloride, with $d_{001} = 18.5 \text{ \AA}$) and Dellite 43B (a layered sodium montmorillonite organically modified by dimethyl, benzyl, hydrogenated tallow, ammonium, with $d_{001} = 18.6 \text{ \AA}$).

The polymer matrix used in the preparation of the hybrids was a commercial copolyamide named Durethan C38F. The nanocomposites were prepared using a twin-screw extruder having co-rotating intermeshing screws ($D = 25$ mm and $L/D=42$). A temperature profile of 240-245-250°C from hopper to die was imposed and screw speeds of 150 and 250 rpm were set.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the meso and nanoscale structure of polymer systems [3] highly affects their viscoelastic response, the relationships between composition, processing conditions, morphology and rheology of melt compounded polyamide was investigated. In Fig.1 the complex viscosity curves of Durethan-based nanocomposites at different types of organoclay and extrusion rates are compared. While the matrix displays a pseudo-Newtonian behaviour in almost the whole range of angular frequency, nanocomposite samples show an higher complex viscosity with increasing the extrusion rate (Fig.1a). In particular, hybrid, with Dellite 43B as filler, displays stronger incremental increases of η^* , with respect to virgin polymer, and a more pronounced “shear thinning” behaviour at a fixed extrusion rate (Fig.1b).

Figure 1 – Complex viscosity curves ($T=250^{\circ}\text{C}$, $\text{strain}=1\%$) for 6wt% Durethan nanocomposites obtained with different extrusion rates and organoclay.

TEM analysis allowed to evidence a strong correlation between the flow curve shape of the nanocomposites and the level of dispersion of the clay platelets inside the polymer matrix. In particular, a better and more uniform exfoliation of the silicate with increasing the extrusion rate and using Dellite 43B as filler was observed.

References

1. Pinnavaia TJ, Beall GW editors, Polymer-Layered Silicate Nanocomposites, N.Y.: John Wiley & Sons Ltd., 2001.
2. Russo GM, Simon GP, Incarnato L. *Macromolecules* 2006, 39: 3855-3864.
3. Ferry JD. *Viscoelastic properties of polymers*, 3rd ed. New York: Wiley; 1980.